

Mass Spectral Studies on Alkyl or Aryltin(IV) and Tin(II) Substituted Oxinates[†]

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The salient features of the mass spectra of several alkyl or aryltin(IV) and tin(II) substituted oxinates of the type $R_2SnL''_2$ ($R=CH_3, C_2H_5, C_4H_9$ or C_6H_5 ; $HL''=2$ - or 5-substituted-8-quinolinol), $R_2SnL''X$ ($R=C_6H_5$; $X=Cl$), R_3SnL'' and SnL''_2 are reported. In the spectra of all the compounds examined, the parent ions are either absent or rather low abundant except in Sn(II) chelates and the fragmentation of the molecular ion by elimination of an alkyl/aryl or a ligand radical is a major mode of dissociation. In all the alkyl/aryltin(IV) and tin(II) chelates, lower metal valency ions occur abundantly. The fragmentation pathways based upon interpretation of spectra and metastable transitions in some 5- and 2-substituted-8-quinolinols are also discussed.

IN recent years, a considerable amount of information has become available on the behaviour, under electron impact conditions of organotin derivatives, such as, tin tetraalkyls¹⁻⁴ or aryls⁵, alkyl or aryltin(IV) halides⁶ and organometallic compounds containing Sn-metal bond⁷. Despite the large volume of mass spectral data on such systems relatively little is known on the fragmentation modes of alkyl or aryltin chelates^{8,9}. As part of a general study on organotin compounds, we have investigated the behaviour under electron impact of some alkyl or aryltin(IV) and tin(II) substituted oxinates along with 5- or 2-substituted-8-quinolinols which are not reported earlier and the results of our studies are presented here. Alkyl or aryltin oxinates are chosen for our investigations because of their stability and convenient volatility.

Experimental

The mass spectra of the compounds were recorded on CEC 21-110B (U.S.A.) double focussing mass spectrometer at a voltage of 70 eV and a current of 20 milliamperes.

Mass spectra of *bis*(8-quinolinolato) diphenyltin(IV)¹⁰ and (8-quinolinolato) triphenyltin(IV)¹¹ are included for comparison since they are not reported earlier.

Bis (8-quinolinolato) diphenyltin(IV): Yield, 65%, m.p. 255°. Found: C, 64.10; H, 3.80; Sn, 20.97%. Required for $C_{80}H_{22}N_2O_2Sn$: C, 64.21; H, 3.92; Sn, 21.17%. (8-quinolinolato) triphenyltin(IV): Yield, 60%, m.p. 144°. Found: C, 65.39; H, 3.97; Sn, 23.89%. Required for $C_{27}H_{21}NOSn$: C, 65.63; H, 4.25; Sn, 24.05%. The synthesis of the other compounds is reported elsewhere^{12,13}.

Results and Discussion

The mass spectra of 2-methyl-8-quinolinol(I), 5-acetyl-8-quinolinol(II), 5-benzoyl-8-quinolinol(III) and 5-phenylazo-8-quinolinol(IV) along with their alkyl or aryltin(IV) and a few tin(II) chelates with I have been recorded. Representative spectra are given in Figs. 1-4. The mass spectral features of 2-methyl-8-quinolinol¹⁴ are similar to those of

Fig. 1. Mass Spectrum of 2-Methyl-8-Quinolinol

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Fig. 2. Mass Spectrum of *bis*(2-Methyl-8-Quinololinolato) Diethyltin(IV).

Fig. 4. Mass Spectrum of *bis*(2-Methyl-8-Quinololinolato) Tin(II).

Fig. 3. Mass Spectrum of (2-Methyl-8-Quinololinolato)Triphenyltin(IV).

clear. It is postulated that $(M-29)^+$ rearranges to

prior to further dissociation. The weak peaks in the m/e 114 to 116 region are presumably due to loss of exocyclic CH_3 group, CO (or CHO) and a hydrogen atom. The low intensity of these peaks is consistent with the low probability of losing a CH_3 group as observed in the mass spectrum of toluene. Relevant mass spectral data for 2- or 5-substituted-8-quinolinols [relative abundance (%) of the principal ions species observed in the spectra] are given in Table I.

8-quinolinol. The main features of the mass spectra of mono-hydroxy substituted quinolines have been discussed previously by Clugston and MacLean¹⁵. In addition to the reported fragmentation pathways some ions originating from $[M-H]^+$ ion have been observed in the spectrum of 2-methyl-8-quinolinol. $[M-H]^+$ ion has been observed as a fairly intense peak and m/e 130 ion which results from the expulsion of CO from this ion is very intense. A metastable peak is observed corresponding to this transition (m^* calculated, 107.9, m^* observed, 107.0). The $(M-29)^+$ might have been formed by a two step process i.e., loss of CO from the molecular ion ($159^+ \rightarrow 131^+ + 28$) followed by the loss of H ($131^+ \rightarrow 130^+ + 1$). The mechanism of loss of HCN from this $(M-29)^+$ is not completely

The base peak in the spectrum of *bis*(2-methyl-8-quinolinolato)dimethyltin(IV) observed is the ion Sn^+L , at m/e 278 formed according to the Scheme I. The molecular ion is not observed. The first reaction, upon electron impact, involving the loss of CH_3 from the molecular ion is shown by the ion m/e 451. The reaction appears to resemble the formation of MR_3^+ ions of high abundance in tin tetraalkyls and related compounds^{16,17}. The loss of a methyl radical is followed by another CH_3 radical forming lower valency state ion $[Sn(L)_2]^+$ at m/e 436. Further elimination of a ligand radical results in the formation of an ion of another lower valency state, $Sn^+(L)$ (m/e 278). The relative abundance of the peak suggests that the species Sn^+L has high stability. Occolowitz¹⁸ in his study

TABLE I—MASS SPECTRAL DATA FOR 2- OR 5-SUBSTITUTED-8-QUINOLINOLS WITH THE GENERAL FORMULA

RELATIVE ABUNDANCE (%) OF THE PRINCIPAL ION SPECIES OBSERVED IN THE SPECTRA OF COMPOUNDS I-IV

Principal Ion	I	II	III	IV
[M] ⁺	91.5	100	90.1	67.7
[M-H]	50.0	<1	7.5	—
[M-CO]	98.8	—	—	—
[M-H-CO]	100	97.4	—	—
[M-CO-H]				
[M-X]	—	64.0	5.8	100
[M-CO-HCN]	75	—	—	—
[M-X-CO]	—	69.6	29.2	40.6
[M-H-CO-HCN]	84.2	7.0	—	—
[M-O ₆ H ₈] or [M-OH ₈]	—	89	100	—
[M-X-CO-HCN]	—	71.2	21.7	—
[M-CO-HCN-2O ₆ H ₈]	54.3	—	—	—
[M-CO-H-HCN-2O ₆ H ₈]	50.6	—	—	—

* I Y=OH; X=H
 II Y=H; X=CH₃CO
 III Y=H; X=C₆H₅CO
 IV Y=H; X=-N=NC₆H₅

the direct loss of the ligand from the parent molecular ion (m/e 308). During the course of the ionization reactions, the ion m/e 159 (HL)⁺ and m/e 158 (ligand-H⁺) are formed and these further undergo metastable supported transformations giving the ions m/e 131, m/e 104, m/e 78 and m/e 52.

In the spectrum of diethyltin(IV) chelate with 2-methyl-8-quinolinol, apart from the loss of a ligand molecule directly from the molecular ion, an ethylene radical elimination is observed (Scheme II). The peak corresponding to the ion Sn⁺L, however, is the most intense. The elimination of ethylene in tetraethyltin and other ethyltin compounds is previously reported by Chambers *et al.*¹⁶

SCHEME - II

SCHEME - I

on electron impact fragmentation of some organotin compounds observed that the fragmentation process giving a new radical ion with lower metal valency appears to occur preferentially in coordination compounds. In covalent tin compounds IVSn⁺R₃, (II⁺SnR₂)⁺, (II⁺Sn⁺R) occur abundantly. In the mass spectra of 2-methyl-8-quinolinol complexes with Al(III), Fernando and Scherer¹⁹ observed the molecular species corresponding to Al(C₁₀H₈NO)₂⁺ (m/e 501) and also low valent species, Al(C₁₀H₈NO)₂⁺ (m/e 343). Recent mass spectral studies on alkyltin(IV) oxinates also have revealed that lower metal valency ions occur abundantly⁹. Another prominent mode of decomposition involves

In the spectra of all the tin chelates metal containing fragment ions appear as a series of peaks close to each other as tin has several naturally occurring isotopes.

In the mass spectra of alkyltin(IV) chelates with 5-substituted-8-quinolinols, parent molecular ions are not observed and the fragments involving the loss of an alkyl radical or ligand are quite abundant. The decomposition patterns are in general similar to those of the chelates discussed above. Although [M-H] is not observed, fragments corresponding to the loss of a ligand or an alkyl radical or both, from this ion are observed as prominent peaks. The peak at m/e 262 observed in the spectra of 5-benzoyl-8-quinolinol and 5-phenylazo-8-quinolinol chelates could arise due to skeletal rearrangement as shown in Scheme III. Several such skeletal rearrangement process accompanied by bond cleavage are reported^{9,10}.

In the mass spectra of di- or triphenyltin(IV) chelates with 8-quinolinol, 2-methyl-8-quinolinol and 5-substituted 8-quinolinols examined here, parent molecular ions are not observed. The fragmentation of the molecular ion by elimination of a ligand or of a ligand followed by both aryl radicals resulting in lower valency state ions (R₂Sn⁺L or R₃Sn⁺, Sn⁺L or RSn⁺) appears to be a major mode of dissociation (Scheme IV). The base peak observed in the spectra of diphenyltin(IV) chelates is the ion Sn⁺L. In triphenyltin(IV) chelates with 5-substituted-8-quinolinol chelates, (M-H) ions are not observed. However, further fragmented ions from

SCHEME - III

SCHEME IV

this ion are present in abundance. The major fragmentation mode in the compound, bis(2-methyl-8-quinolinolato)diphenyltin(IV) apparently involves the loss of $C_{12}H_{10}$ radical²¹⁻²⁴ followed by the loss of a ligand radical. The ion at m/e 274, $[(C_6H_5)_2Sn]$ is apparently formed by the loss of two ligand radicals from the molecular ion and seems to be stable. Loss of an aryl radical from this ion results in the formation of a low valent species, $C_6H_5Sn^+$ (m/e 197).

In both the spectra of Sn(II) chelates, bis(2-methyl-8-quinolinolato)tin(II) and chloro(2-methyl-8-quinolinolato)tin(II), parent molecular ions are observed. However, the peaks corresponding to the ion Sn^+L (m/e 278) and Sn^+Cl (m/e 155) formed by the loss of a ligand radical from the respective molecular ions, are the most abundant. In the spectrum of chloro-(2-methyl-8-quinolinolato)tin(II), direct loss of a Cl from the parent ion at m/e 278 is also observed.

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